

DEVELOPING NEURO-SYMBOLIC CONVERSATIONAL SYSTEMS FOR RELIABLE MULTI-PERSPECTIVE PRODUCTION PROCESS INTELLIGENCE

Angelo Casciani¹, Livia Lestingi²,
Andrea Marrella¹, Andrea Matta²

SAPIENZA¹
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

POLITECNICO²
MILANO 1863

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

CAISE '26

Verona, Italy
11 June 2026

WHO WE ARE

Angelo Casciani

PhD Student in AI on Neuro-Symbolic AI for Information Systems (ends in Jan 2027)

Livia Lestingi

Junior Assistant Professor on Software Engineering for Cyber-Physical Systems

Andrea Marrella

Associate Professor of Engineering in Computer Science

Andrea Matta

Professor on Analysis, Design and Management of Manufacturing Systems

TUTORIAL OUTLINE

- Introduction & State of the Art
- Why Standalone LLMs are Not Enough
- The Neuro-Symbolic Paradigm for Conversational Systems
- Case Study: The Manufacturing Silo Problem
- Hands-on & Walkthrough
- Concluding Remarks

INTRODUCTION & STATE OF THE ART

THE EVOLUTION OF AI RESEARCH

Rule-based AI
[1950's]

Step by step logic
& instructions
coded by human
developers

Machine Learning
[1980's]

Human crafted
features with
supervised learning
to analyze data for
a specific task

Deep Learning
[2010's]

Autonomous
features
identification in
machine learning

Generative AI
[2020's]

Unsupervised AI that
ingests massive
amount of data to
generate new
human-like text, art,
images, video, etc.

Source: <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/artificial-intelligence>

SYMBOLIC AND SUBSYMBOLIC AI

Symbolic AI

- Also known as rule-based or traditional AI
- It relies on a knowledge base represented in the form of logic-based symbols or rules

Subsymbolic AI

- Subsymbolic (neural) AI focuses on creating intelligent behaviour by learning patterns from data rather than relying on explicit rules
- It involves processing and analysing data using numerical methods and statistical models to solve problems, eliminating the need for explicit rules or algorithms

O. Yalcin. [Black-box and White-Box Models towards Explainable AI](#). Web. Jun. 23, 2021

SYMBOLIC AND SUBSYMBOLIC AI

O. Yalcin. Symbolic vs. Subsymbolic AI Paradigms for AI Explainability. Web. Jun. 21, 2021

HISTORY OF LANGUAGE MODELS

What is a Language Model?

- A language model is a probabilistic model of natural language
- Since the 1960s, AI researchers have been trying to teach machines to understand natural language
- They have advanced from early rule-based models, such as ELIZA, to modern artificial neural network-based architectures

M. Ghaseminejad Raeini, The evolution of language models: From N-Grams to LLMs, and beyond, Natural Language Processing 12, 100168 (2025)

VISUALIZING ATTENTION

Attention-matrix heatmap

Bahdanau, et al. 2015. Neural machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate. In Proc. ICLR.

Self-attention

J. Alammar. [Visualizing A Neural Machine Translation Model \(Mechanics of Seq2seq Models With Attention\)](#). Web. May 9, 2018

J. Alammar. [The Illustrated Transformer](#). Web. Jun. 27, 2018

TRANSFORMER ARCHITECTURE

“Attention is All You Need”

- A transformer is a deep learning architecture by Google based on the multi-head self-attention mechanism
- Its advantage is that it has no recurrent units. It is originally composed of an encoder and a decoder part

What makes a model “large”

- The introduction of the transformer architecture enabled the training of models with **billions of parameters**. Today, bigger models are reaching one trillion parameters.
- It remains at the core of modern Large Language Models.

A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, et al., Attention is all you need, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS) 30 (2017)

LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Harnessing the Power of LLMs in Practice: A Survey on ChatGPT and Beyond

J. Yang, H. Jin, R. Tang, X. Han, et al, Harnessing the Power of LLMs in Practice: A Survey on ChatGPT and Beyond. ACM Trans. Knowl. Discov. Data. 18, 6, 160 (2024)

ENCODER-ONLY ARCHITECTURE

- It takes in a sequence of tokens and produces a fixed-size vector representation of the whole sequence.
- It can then be used for classification.

ENCODER-DECODER ARCHITECTURE

- It is used for tasks such as language translation, where the input is a sentence in one language and the model outputs an equivalent sentence in another.

STATE-OF-THE-ART ARCHITECTURES

S. Raschka, The Big LLM architecture Comparison, Web, Apr. 2, 2026

PRE-TRAINING OF LLMs

- Foundational step in the LLM training, in which the model gains a general understanding of language through exposure to vast amounts of text data, in an unsupervised manner
- After it, the model is generally not capable of solving specific problems.

Most common pre-training task:

- **Masked Language Modeling:** *"The quick brown fox jumps over the ___ (lazy) dog."*
- **Next Sentence Prediction:** *"The scientist made a groundbreaking discovery. ___ (She was awarded the Nobel Prize)."*
- **Contrastive Learning:** *"Hope is the thing with feathers – / That perches in the soul – / And sings the tune without the words – / And never stops at all – (Similar)"*
- **Permutation Language Modeling:** *"the sky blue is so" -> "so blue is the sky"*

SPECIALIZING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Fractal. [Governing Large Language Models through enhancing techniques](#). Web. Mar. 2024

WHY STANDALONE LLMS ARE NOT ENOUGH

SENSITIVITY TO PARAPHRASING

LLM effectiveness declines when questions are paraphrased

- High benchmark scores may not capture a model's true robustness
- High consistency across paraphrases is not a proxy for correctness
- Extreme sensitivity to wording makes standalone LLMs unreliable for real-world tasks

R. Lunardi, V. D. Mea, S. Mizzaro, K. Roitero, On Robustness and Reliability of Benchmark-based Evaluation of LLMs. ECAI 2025, Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications, IOS Press (2025)

THE PLANNING GAP

LLMs are Approximate Retrievers

- LLMs generate tokens at a constant rate, which is incompatible with the principled reasoning required for planning
- Models do not “plan” but perform approximate retrieval of plan heuristics
- LLMs lack internal mechanisms for self-verification

Domain	Method	Instances correct					
		GPT-4o	GPT-4-Turbo	Claude-3-Opus	LLaMA-3 70B	Gemini Pro	GPT-4
Blocksworld (BW)	One-shot	170/600 (28.33%)	138/600 (23%)	289/600 (48.17%)	76/600 (12.6%)	68/600 (11.3%)	206/600 (34.3%)
	Zero-shot	213/600 (35.5%)	241/600 (40.1%)	356/600 (59.3%)	205/600 (34.16%)	3/600 (0.5%)	210/600 (34.6%)
Mystery BW (Deceptive)	One-shot	5/600 (0.83%)	5/600 (0.83%)	8/600 (1.3%)	15/600 (2.5%)	2/500 (0.4%)	26/600 (4.3%)
	Zero-shot	0/600 (0%)	1/600 (0.16%)	0/600 (0%)	0/600 (0%)	0/500 (0%)	1/600 (0.16%)

S. Kambhampati, K. Valmeekam, L. Guan, M. Verma, et al., Position: LLMs Can't Plan, But Can Help Planning in LLM-Modulo Frameworks, ICML 2024, OpenReview.net (2024)

K. Stechly, K. Valmeekam, S. Kambhampati, On the Self-Verification Limitations of Large Language Models on Reasoning and Planning Tasks, ICLR 2025, OpenReview.net (2025)

THE ILLUSION OF REASONING TRACES

Large Reasoning Models (LRMs) Still Performs Pattern Matching

- *Chain-of-Thought* traces are just learned structural patterns. Final answers may follow intermediate "reasoning" traces that are logically flawed or even incorrect
- While verbose traces can improve task performance, human users rate them as **least interpretable**
- LRMs may offer **seemingly reasonable justifications** for incorrect answers, "gaslighting" users
- The number of "reasoning tokens" generated **does not correlate** with the computational complexity

S. Kambhampati, K. Valmeekam, S. Bhambri, V. Palod, Position: Stop Anthropomorphizing Intermediate Tokens as Reasoning/Thinking Traces!, arXiv preprint, arxiv: 2505.13792 (2025)

S. Bhambri, U. Biswas, S. Kambhampati, Interpretable traces, unexpected outcomes: Investigating the disconnect in trace-based knowledge distillation, arXiv preprint, arxiv: 2505.13792 (2025)

K. Valmeekam, K. Stechly, A. Gundawar, S. Kambhampati, A Systematic Evaluation of the Planning and Scheduling Abilities of the Reasoning Model o1, Transactions on Machine Learning Research (2025)

TAXONOMY OF LLM REASONING FAILURES

P. Song, P. Han, N. Goodman, Large Language Model Reasoning Failures, Trans. Mach. Learn. Res. (2026)

LLMS MISS THE MULTI-AGENT MARK

Improper MAS Terminology

- Most current agentic frameworks use single-agent prompting techniques, which overlook concurrency and shared states.

Lack of Native Social Behavior

- LLMs are trained in isolation to respond to users rather than to interact with each other.

Environment Design Flaws

- MAS LLM environments are overly "LLM-centric", relying on ambiguous natural language for representation.

Communication Ambiguity

- Over-reliance on free-text communication is expensive and inefficient.
- MAS requires structured languages and protocols (e.g., KQML).

E. La Malfa, G. La Malfa, S. Marro, J. M. Zhang, E. Black, M. Luck, P. Torr, M. J. Wooldridge, Large Language Models Miss the Multi-Agent Mark, NeurIPS 2025, (2025)

THE NEURO-SYMBOLIC PARADIGM FOR CONVERSATIONAL SYSTEMS

ML/DL VS GENERATIVE AI

ML/DL: Learn to perform a specific task

- Typical tasks: classification, prediction, recommendation
- Example: recognize digits and letters
- Usually trained for a narrowly defined objective

Generative AI: Learn to generate new content (text, images, videos)

- LLMs generate the next most probable token given the context
- Very general: expected to be able to solve any problem
- Example: question-answering, write code, create images
- Knowledge depends on training data and may be incomplete/outdated
- Trained to predict the next token; problem-solving emerge from this
 - May generate plausible but incorrect information, i.e., hallucinations

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE - HUMAN LAZINESS

Lawyer cited 6 fake cases made up by ChatGPT; judge calls it "unprecedented"

L. Huang, W. Yu, W. Ma, W. Zhong, et al., A Survey on Hallucination in Large Language Models: Principles, Taxonomy, Challenges, and Open Questions, ACM Trans. Inf. Syst. 43 (2) (2025) 42:1–42:55.

REASONING IN HUMANS

Reasoning Tasks

- Humans need reasoning (System 2) to solve them
 - Ex.: complex arithmetic
- Possibly in combination with experience (System 1)
 - Ex.: language translation

Non-reasoning Tasks

- Humans just use System 1
 - Ex.: face recognition

Skill Learning

- From System 2 to System 1: from reasoning to retrieval
 - Ex: Reading, driving, ...

McIntyre, P.: [52 Concepts To Add To Your Cognitive Toolkit](#). Web. Sept. 23, 2016.

Kahneman, D.: Thinking, Fast and Slow. Penguin, London (2012)

*“Since the triumphs of machine learning in 2012, AI produces solutions by the **opaque operations of large neural net**, which shares many features with the automatic intuitions of System 1. The **integration of intuition and reasoning** in AI was **not achieved** during the first decade of the machine learning era.”*

Daniel Kahneman on current AI (Dec. 2023)

IS THE NEW REASONING REALLY REASONING?

Reasoning is a process, not just the result of that process

- A reasoner adopts a reasoning process
- Trustworthy, explainable, correct
- But also rigid, needs humans doing the modeling of the problem

Reasoner in ML/Generative AI is the approximation of the I/O behavior of a reasoner

- With no guarantee of the approximation quality
- Non trustworthy (can produce hallucinations), need to check on trusted sources
- Retrieval of previously memorized solutions, rather than reasoning from first principles
- Out of distribution / outliers' issue
- Reasoner simulators

IS ONE BETTER THAN THE OTHER ONE?

Depending on the use case, one may employ a formal reasoner or a reasoner simulator

Formal Reasoner

- When we care about 100% correctness and consistency
- When we need a trace of the reasoning values used to generate the output

Reasoner Simulator

- When we don't care how the output is generated
- When we don't care that the system is always consistent and correct

CAN THEY HELP EACH OTHER?

Reasoner simulators may be incorrect

- They can be combined with a reasoner for increased correctness, consistency, reduced resource consumption and automated modeling
- Ex.: LLM-modulo, Alpha-Geometry

Formal reasoners do not have a flexible model of the world

- Unless we explicitly provide it to them
- They can be combined with reasoner simulators to get a model and improve their flexibility and performance
- Ex: Alpha-Geometry

Neuro-Symbolic AI

- Need for introspection and meta-cognition for either internal (in the ML architecture) or external combination

THE NEURO-SYMBOLIC AI LANDSCAPE

Perception meets Logic

- Neuro-symbolic AI merges connectionist learning (neural networks) with the precision of symbolic reasoning to create systems that can learn and think.
- The "neuro" component acts as a perception engine, processing unstructured sensory data to identify patterns, while the "symbolic" component acts as a reasoning engine, applying explicit rules and causal logic.

Neuro-Symbolic Decision-Making

- Mimics the human brain by integrating System 1 (fast, intuitive, pattern-based) with System 2 (slow, deliberate, rule-based) thinking.
- Overcomes the "black box" nature of neural networks by grounding their outputs in interpretable symbolic representations, making the AI's "thought process" transparent to human operators.

B. P. Bhuyan, A. Ramdane-Cherif, Ravi Tomar, T. P. Singh, Neuro-symbolic artificial intelligence: a survey, Neural Computing and Applications 36 (2024)

LLM SHIFT: FROM SOLVER TO FORMALIZER

APPROACH	LLM-AS-PLANNER	LLM-AS-FORMALIZER
<i>Role</i>	Generates plan	Translates to PDDL
<i>Execution</i>	Direct	Delegated to symbolic planner
<i>Reliability</i>	Struggles	Sound

M. Tantakoun, C. Muise, X. Zhu: LLMs as Planning Formalizers: A Survey for Leveraging Large Language Models to Construct Automated Planning Models. Findings of the ACL 2025. ACL (2025)

THE "LLM-MODULO" PARADIGM

The Generate-Test-Critique Loop

- The LLM acts as a formalizer, to translate ambiguous natural language into structured representations
- Iterative framework where the LLM "guesses" a candidate solution and a group of external sound verifiers check it for correctness
- By offloading the reasoning to symbolic solvers, the framework provides mathematical correctness guarantees that a standalone LLM cannot provide

S. Kambhampati, K. Valmeekam, L. Guan, M. Verma, et al., Position: LLMs Can't Plan, But Can Help Planning in LLM-Modulo Frameworks, ICML 2024, OpenReview.net (2024)

NEURO-SYMBOLIC PROCESS INTELLIGENCE

SYSTEM 1
<i>Fast, intuitive, data-driven</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good at learning, poor at reasoning • Data-hungry • Uninterpretable • Prone to hallucinations • Scalable • Grounded in language use
Generative AI

SYSTEM 2
<i>Slow, deliberative, reason-based</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good at reasoning, poor at learning • Data-efficient • Interpretable • Hallucination-free • Hand-crafted • Grounded in facts
Symbolic AI

Kahneman, D.: Thinking, fast and slow. Penguin, London (2012)

The human mind combines both.

If we can figure out how to combine the best of both worlds, we can create a conversational system that is interpretable, verifiable, yet responsive to data.

THE NEURO-SYMBOLIC CONVERSATIONAL SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE FOR PROCESS INTELLIGENCE

CASE STUDY: THE MANUFACTURING SILO PROBLEM

INDUSTRY 5.0

The Industry 5.0 Paradigm Shift

- Builds upon Industry 4.0 by shifting the focus from pure automation to human-centricity, sustainability, and balanced human-machine collaboration.

LLMs for Industry 5.0?

- LLMs act as catalysts for resilience and innovation by enhancing human-centred processes rather than merely automating repetitive tasks.
- However, LLMs rely on probabilistic pattern recognition.
- While LLMs can mimic reasoning, they lack the true logical inference required for reliable task execution in Industry 5.0.

P. K. Gantayat, T. Kaur, M. Majhi, U. K. Jena, From Efficiency to Innovation: LLM 5.0 and the Future of Industry. Int. Conf. on Multi-Agent Systems for Collaborative Intelligence (ICMSCI), IEEE (2025)

PRODUCTION PROCESS INTELLIGENCE (PPI)

Objectives

- Combine production data and digital models to enhance decision-making
- Foster human-production system collaboration

PPI tools are deterministic inference engines,
accessed via standardized APIs

DISCRETE EVENT SIMULATION	PROCESS MINING	VERIFICATION
Predictive	Descriptive	Safety Checks

Use Case

“As a plant manager, I need to make a real-time decision by combining a safety check with what-if analysis of the production.”

S. Agostinelli, D. Benvenuti, A. Casciani, F. De Luzi, M. Marinacci, A. Marrella, J. Rossi. A Context-Aware Framework to Support Decision-Making in Production Planning, CAISE 2024 (2024)

Z. Keskin, D. Joosten, N. Klasen, M. Huber, et al. LLM Enhanced Human-Machine Interaction for Adaptive Decision-Making in Dynamic Manufacturing Process Environments, IEEE Access 13 (2025)

DISCRETE EVENT SIMULATION

- *What-if* analysis without disrupting operations
- Implementation: SimPy

N. Matloff, Introduction to Discrete-Event Simulation and the SimPy Language, Davis, CA. Dept of Computer Science. University of California at Davis. 2 (2009)

Zhang, L, Zhou, L, Ren, L, Laili, Y.: Modeling and simulation in intelligent manufacturing. Computers in Industry 112, 103123 (2019)

Digital Twin

Scenario

KPIs

Use Case

“As a production manager, I need to establish a performance baseline, plan a production target, and assess the impact of a machine breakdown.”

PROCESS MINING

Process Intelligence Solutions. [PM4Py](#). Web. Jun, 2026

- Operates on event logs from shop-floor
- Implementation: PM4Py

Four tasks

- Discovery → Petri Net
- Conformance Checking → Deviations
- Time Filtering → Filtered Event Log
- Performance Analysis → KPIs, Variants

Use Case

“As a process analyst, I have a raw event log and I want to discover the underlying Petri net, check if reality matches the model, and then analyze execution frequencies.”

VERIFICATION

- Safety guarantees via model checking
- Implementation: UPPAAL

Larsen, K.G., Pettersson, P., Yi, W.: UPPAAL in a nutshell. Int. J. Softw. Tools Technol. Transf. 1(1-2), 134-152 (1997)

Automaton

Property

Boolean
Result

Use Case

“As a safety engineer, I want to audit the production system by understanding the automaton semantics, verifying global safety, and checking specific temporal behaviors.”

PPI: ARE WE REALLY OKAY WITH THIS?

The “Silo” Problem

- Technical expertise required
- Fragmented interfaces
- Manual, slow, and error-prone decision-making

□ Each PPI tool: different expertise, formats, languages

Simulation

Process Mining

Verification

Z. Keskin, D. Joosten, N. Klasen, M. Huber, et al. LLM Enhanced Human–Machine Interaction for Adaptive Decision–Making in Dynamic Manufacturing Process Environments, IEEE Access 13 (2025)

N. Frigerio, B. Tan, A. Matta. Simultaneous control of multiple machines for energy efficiency: a simulation–based approach, Int. J. Prod. Res. 62 (3) (2024)

S. Agostinelli, D. Benvenuti, A. Casciani, F. De Luzi, M. Marinacci, A. Marrella, J. Rossi. A Context–Aware Framework to Support Decision–Making in Production Planning, CAISE 2024, Advanced Inf. Sys. Engineering, Springer(2024)

MULTI-PERSPECTIVE ANALYSIS

Multi-Perspective Analysis Require Manual Integration

□ User → Manual orchestration → Multiple tools → Manual integration

Example: A massive new order arrives.

NEURO-SYMBOLIC CONVERSATIONAL SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTION PROCESS INTELLIGENCE

GitHub Repository

Extension of:
 A. Casciani, L. Lestingi, A. Marrella, A. Matta, A Conversational Framework for Faithful Multi-perspective Analysis of Production Systems, CAISE 2025, Springer (2025)

INTENT ROUTING AND PPI ORCHESTRATION VIA PLANNING

Intent Routing

- Analyzes natural language query → identifies intent

Routing logic

- Single tool → Forward to Encoder
- Multi-perspective → Forward to Planner

Orchestration

- LLM encodes intents in PDDL goals
- Symbolic AI planner (*Fast Downward*) → sound plan

M. Helmert, The Fast Downward Planning System, J. Artif. Intell. Res. 26 191–246 (2006)

ENCODING & RESPONSE

- Specialized encoder LLM for each PPI tool (avoids interference)
- Planned actions → Encoded JSON payload → PPI tool execution → Result

Soundness Guarantee

- Computation occurs outside LLMs → Reliable results

DATA LAYER

- Event log (in XES) from shop-floor sensors
- Automated models extraction (no manual modeling)

EXTRACTOR	OUTPUT	USED BY
Digital Twin	Scenario parameters	Simulation
Automata Learning	Probabilistic Timed Automaton	Verification
-	Raw log	Process Mining

HANDS-ON & WALKTHROUGH

CASE STUDY: THE LEGO FACTORY

Small-scale replica of a processing plant from the automotive field using the Lego Mindstorms kit, grounded in the Italian PRIN project MOTOWN.

A. Casciani, L. Lestingi, A. Marrella, A. Matta, A Conversational Framework for Faithful Multi-perspective Analysis of Production Systems, CAiSE 2025, Springer (2025)
D. Mindell, C. Beland, W. Chan, D. Clarke, R. Park, M. Trupiano, LEGO Mindstorms, The Structure of an Engineering Revolution (2000).

HANDS-ON SESSION

Let's see the system in action!

A. Casciani, F. Italia, L. Lestingi, M. Marinacci, A. Marrella, A. Matta, FIDES: A Neuro-Symbolic Conversational Tool for Faithful Production Process Intelligence, CAISE Forum 2026, Springer (2026)

COOL! BUT...

What is really happening
under the hood?

RECEIVING THE QUESTION

INTENT PROCESSING & PLANNING

DISPATCHING & ENCODING

PPI TASKS EXECUTION

ANSWER GENERATION

ACCURACY BENCHMARK

LLM	Zero-Shot						Few-Shot					
	<i>R</i>	<i>SI</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>PM</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>MP</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>SI</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>PM</i>	<i>ST</i>	<i>MP</i>
<i>llama-3-8b</i>	0.66	0.74	0.76	1.00	0.98	0.43	0.70	0.79	0.78	1.00	0.98	0.52
<i>llama-3.1-8b</i>	0.72	0.52	0.67	1.00	0.96	0.58	0.76	0.76	0.73	1.00	0.98	0.58
<i>llama-3.2-1b</i>	0.10	0.43	0.02	0.43	0.73	0.04	0.21	0.48	0.02	0.52	0.81	0.08
<i>llama-3.2-3b</i>	0.64	0.80	0.58	0.95	0.98	0.40	0.68	0.86	0.64	0.95	0.98	0.44
<i>mistral-7b-v0.2</i>	0.71	0.90	0.79	0.96	<u>0.99</u>	0.50	0.76	0.93	0.82	1.00	<u>0.99</u>	0.56
<i>mistral-7b-v0.3</i>	0.81	0.98	0.74	<u>0.98</u>	1.00	0.34	0.83	0.98	0.76	1.00	1.00	0.42
<i>mistral-nemo</i>	0.87	0.88	0.68	1.00	1.00	0.58	0.91	0.92	0.72	1.00	1.00	0.63
<i>ministral-8b</i>	0.77	<u>0.99</u>	0.78	1.00	1.00	0.62	0.80	<u>0.99</u>	0.80	1.00	1.00	0.68
<i>qwen2.5-7b</i>	0.81	<u>0.94</u>	0.82	1.00	1.00	0.46	0.85	<u>0.94</u>	0.85	1.00	1.00	0.56
<i>gemma-2-9b</i>	0.61	0.94	0.82	0.97	0.96	0.37	0.65	0.96	0.83	1.00	1.00	0.41
<i>phi-4</i>	0.90	0.47	0.86	0.89	1.00	0.77	0.90	0.54	0.86	0.92	1.00	0.83
<i>gemini-2.5-flash</i>	0.99	0.98	0.98	1.00	0.90	0.94	0.99	<u>0.99</u>	0.99	1.00	0.92	<u>0.95</u>
<i>gemini-2.5-pro</i>	0.99	0.89	0.80	1.00	0.72	<u>0.95</u>	0.99	<u>0.93</u>	0.83	1.00	0.84	<u>0.95</u>
<i>gpt-5.1</i>	<u>0.98</u>	1.00	<u>0.87</u>	1.00	1.00	0.97	<u>0.98</u>	1.00	<u>0.90</u>	1.00	1.00	0.99

ACCURACY VARIABILITY

Accuracy distribution across tasks by LLM in the zero-shot setting

Accuracy distribution across tasks by LLM in the few-shot setting

IS IT REALLY BETTER THAN AN LLM? YES!

METHOD	SIMULATION (MAPE)	VERIFICATION (ACCURACY)
<i>Random</i>	353,761% ± 32,834	49% ± 10
<i>LLM-only (llama-3.2-1b)</i>	91,393%	12%
<i>LLM-only (llama-3.1-8b)</i>	85,420%	38%
<i>LLM-only (ministral-8b)</i>	78,104%	41%
<i>LLM-only (gemini-2.5-flash)</i>	145,243%	46%
<i>LLM-only (gemini-2.5-pro)</i>	102,540%	51%
Neuro-symbolic	0.00%	100.00%

ENCODING HALLUCINATION PATTERNS

TASK	ERROR TYPE	DESCRIPTION	PREVALENT IN	EXAMPLE
Routing	<i>Semantic Ambiguity</i>	Outputs multiple labels instead of returning a single routing decision	<i>llama-3.2-1B</i>	User: "Check if state x is reachable." LLM: "I would respond with factory_simulation or uppaal_verification."
	<i>Stop Token Failure</i>	Correctly identifies the intent but fails to stop generation, producing code or explanations instead of a routing label.	<i>gemma-2-9b</i>	User: "Show me the most frequent 9 variants from the event log." LLM: "def route query(...): return 'process mining'"
Simulation	<i>Hallucinated Execution Results</i>	Fabricates execution results instead of generating the JSON encoding for the PPI tool.	<i>llama-3.2-1B</i>	User: "Simulate the process to produce 350 pieces." LLM: "Simulation results. Station 1: 25 pieces ... Total: 525."
Verification	<i>Formal Syntax Hallucination</i>	Generates syntactically invalid UPPAAL queries using made-up constructs.	<i>llama-3.2-1B</i>	User: "Does the process always reach event x?" LLM: "A[s.init] && E[s.x]"
Process Mining	<i>Parameter Value Hallucination</i>	Produces syntactically valid JSON but includes not supported parameter values.	<i>llama-3.2-1B</i>	User: "What is the mean throughput time?" LLM: "{...\"metric\" : \"mean_throughput_time\" ...}"
Structural Information	<i>Instruction Following Violation</i>	Retrieves the correct information from PPI tools but ignores the required JSON output format.	<i>mistral-7B-v0.2</i>	User: "What is the inter-arrival time?" LLM: "The mean inter-arrival time is 300s."
Multi-Perspective	<i>Logical Decomposition Failure</i>	Does not recognize all required tasks in multi-perspective queries.	<i>mistral-nemo</i>	User: "Produce 50 pieces, station 4 may fail, verify if event x is reachable." LLM: JSON with no failure task

CONCLUDING REMARKS

OUTLOOK

A Conversational Methodology for Production Process Intelligence

- Introduced the steps to develop neuro-symbolic conversational AI systems, combining LLMs with PPI engines, for faithful, multi-perspective analysis of production systems.
- Transitioning LLMs from flawed PPI executors to flexible formalizers:
 - the LLM encodes and redirect;
 - the symbolic engines handle orchestration and computation.

Application & Future Improvements

- The aim is not to replace human experts, but rather to use LLMs as intuitive interfaces that make complex PPI tools more accessible.
- While demonstrated on a manufacturing use case, this framework is domain-agnostic.
- Future work, such as targeted fine-tuning, can help mitigating encoding hallucinations and streamline the modeling effort currently required to define tool planning schemas.

CAISE '26

Verona, Italy

11 June 2026

THANK YOU

Presented by

Angelo Casciani and Andrea Marrella

Mail: {casciani, marrella}@diag.uniroma1.it

Zenodo

About A. Casciani

About A. Marrella

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

PRE-TRAINING OF LLMs

Foundational step in the LLM training process, in which the model gains a general understanding of language through exposure to vast amounts of text data, in an unsupervised manner. It is called pre-training because, after it, the model is generally not capable of solving specific problems.

Most common pre-training task:

- **Masked Language Modeling:** *"The quick brown fox jumps over the ___ (lazy) dog."*
- **Next Sentence Prediction:** *"The scientist made a groundbreaking discovery. ___ (She was awarded the Nobel Prize)."*
- **Contrastive Learning:** *"Hope is the thing with feathers – / That perches in the soul – / And sings the tune without the words – / And never stops at all – (Similar)"*
- **Permutation Language Modeling:** *"the sky blue is so" -> "so blue is the sky"*

PROMPT FOR SIMULATION

Prompt for the Encoder LLM for Production Simulation

Act as a conversational interface towards the digital twin of the LEGO factory.

Role & Task

Use the following pieces of context to generate from the user question a JSON object containing one of the allowed 'task':

- 'sim_with_time' for the number of pieces produced in a certain time and related metrics (e.g. processing time);
- 'sim_with_number_products' to know how much units of time needed to produce a certain number of pieces and related metrics (e.g. processing time);
- 'event_prediction' for predicting the next station.

If the user question does not match an allowed tasks kindly refuse to answer.

The allowed values for 'task' are: 'sim_with_time', 'sim_with_number_products', 'event_prediction'.

Context

The labels for the stations are: station11, station21, station22, station31, station41, ...

Examples:

Examples

1. Input (Natural Language Query): Carry out a simulation for 1000 units of time to check how many pieces are produced.

Output (LLM answer): {"task": "sim_with_time", "simulation_time": 1000, "target_pieces": "", "stations_sequence": [], "query_nl": "Carry out a simulation for 1000 units of time to check how many pieces are produced."}

...

Perform 5 simulation replicas with a warm-up period of 200 seconds. After the warm-up, simulate the production of 100 pieces and report the average processing time for station31.

Input

PROMPT FOR MULTI-PERSPECTIVE QUERIES

Prompt for Multi-Perspective Requests

Act as an assistant that translates natural language queries into a JSON object containing a valid PDDL problem instance.

Role & Task

The problem must conform to a given PDDL domain and define:

- The requests expressed as objects.
- Their type (processes, inputs, ...)
- An appropriate goal that triggers the correct reasoning process (e.g., (has_time o), (reachable s), etc.).

The final output should be a JSON object like:

```
{ "task": "hybrid", "pddl_problem": "(define (problem reasoners_prob) (:domain reasoners) (:objects ...) (:init ...) (:goal ...))"
  "questions": [{"question": "...", "type": "simulation"}, {"question": "...", "type": "validation"}]}
```

The type field takes value in one of the following: "simulation", "validation", "failure". The 'questions' list must contain natural language sub-questions, one for each task.

Only output a JSON object without any explanation or extra formatting.

If the problem does not have a target activity, use activity1 as target activity.

If there is no explicit information that the digital twin is already obtained or the system is deadlock free, do not put the corresponding predicates in the initial condition of the PDDL problem.

PDDL domain + stations in the production system

Context

Examples:

Examples

1. Input (Natural Language Query): "How much time is needed to produce 50 pieces given that activity 4 is expected to fail? Also, validate if the system remains deadlock free during production."

Output (LLM answer): {"task": "hybrid", "pddl_problem": "(define (problem reasoners_prob) (:domain reasoners) (:objects I - input P - process O - output S1 S2 S3 S4 S5 - activity) (:init (has_pieces I) (requires_maintenance S4) (is_maintained S1) (is_maintained S2) (is_maintained S3) (is_maintained S5) (target_activity S4)) (:goal (and (has_time O) (deadlock_free P) (is_maintained S4))))", "questions": [{"question": "How much time is needed to produce 50 pieces?", "type": "simulation"}, {"question": "What are the failure patterns of activity4?", "type": "failure"}, {"question": "Is the system deadlock free during the production process?", "type": "validation"}]} ...

Perform 5 simulation replicas from an empty initial state: can 40 products be made within 300 units of time assuming that station11 fails? Validate also if the event s1 is reachable.

Input